

MXR Autumn cruise 12-14 October

The cruise was planned to go to Malangsdjupet to investigate the exchange of overwintering copepods between shelf and ocean. It is part of the Migratory Crossroad project that looks at diel and seasonal rhythms of copepods, and also part of the master studies of Anni Joamets, a seasonal study of overwintering *Calanus*. Due to very heavy weather it was not possible to go to the outer part, so we went to two fjords and one a bit outer station (station 4) and were happy to find large amounts of overwintering *Calanus* there.

Our **sampling approach** consisted of:

- 1) **CTD sampling** with water at bottom, 50, 20, 10, 5 and 0 m for chlorophyll *a* (filtered and analysed on board) and nutrients (frozen at -20 °C), and for stable isotope (SI) analyses of POM (2 liter filtered from 20 m, frozen at -20 °C),
- 2) **WP2** (180 µm) net sampling for biomass (2 size fractions: 180-500 µm and > 500 µm), taxonomy (fixed in 96% ethanol) and for picking *Calanus* CV for SI analyses (3 replicates of 10 individuals, frozen in tin cups at -20 °C) and for lipid analyses (frozen in lipid glasses at -80 °C). In general we sampled two layers, from bottom to ca. 150 m and from 50-0 m.
- 3) **LOPC** sampling, 3 profiles to bottom.
- 4) **ADCP and EK60** data were logged continuously

Saturday 12th October

We left at 8:00 and headed straight to **Ullsfjorden**, where we sampled an outer station (station 1), a station in the middle of the fjord just with the LOPC (station 2), and a station in the inner part (station 3) in the evening. During the night we sampled an ADCP and EK60 transect out to our outermost station 4 and from there another acoustic transect into Lyngsfjorden and back to station 4.

In the outer part of Ullsfjorden there were very many *Calanus* at depth, in overwintering mode, with antennae by the side of the body and not reacting much to touching. This was in stark contrast to the inner station, where we observed very, very few individuals. In Ullsfjorden, as at all the other stations, low chlorophyll *a* values of around 0.3 mg m⁻³ were measured. The upper layer (50-60 m) in both fjords was well mixed.

Sunday 13th October

We started with our **outer station 4**, which is located between Vannøya and Arnøya, after breakfast (8:00), and then headed to the outer station in **Lyngsfjorden** (station 5), which we started at 14:00. Here, wind was at 17 m s⁻¹ and we decided to not sample the upper layer with a WP2 in order to not risk the net. From station 4 onwards we just sampled biomass from the lower layer, because we were running out of trays for biomass samples. After station 5 we continued over the sill into the inner part of the fjord and completed station 6 there (wind around 13 m s⁻¹). This was our last full station and we started packing in the evening.

Also at station 4, there were very many overwintering *Calanus* at depth, they seemed slightly more active than the ones in outer Ullsfjorden. The acoustic transects in the night indicated some diel migration of larger organisms. The same pattern of many overwintering *Calanus*, which were all slightly more active than the ones in Ullsfjorden, was found at both stations in Lyngsfjorden, also at the inner station behind the sill (station 6).

Monday 14th October

We repeated the **LOPC sampling at station 2** in the early morning (0:30), because during the previous sampling the LOPC had stopped recording data before it reached the bottom and only one profile. After that we headed straight back to Tromsø, where we arrived around 5 in the morning, but continued packing and cleaned after breakfast.

Despite the bad weather surrounding us, we can look back at a successful cruise during which we did manage to sample overwintering copepods in two fjords. These different parts of the *Calanus* population may or may not be linked to those at the outer station 4, which the SI analyses will shed light upon.

Cruise participants

Sünnje L. Basedow	UiT	Cruise leader, MXR WP2
Kanchana Bandara	APN	Project leader
Pierre Priou	APN	MXR WP2
Elisabeth Halvorsen	UiT	Technician
Anni Joamets	UiT	Master student

Sampling overview – position and ship deployment number

The Lyngsfjorden acoustic transect was logged by the ship, number 1472.

Station	Latitude	Longitude	CTDs	WP2s	LOPC
St. 1 Ullsfj. outer	69.7763	19.8094	1459	1460-1463	1464
St. 2 Ullsfj. centre	69.7301	19.7560	-	-	1465*,1490
St. 3 Ullsfj. inner	69.6731	19.7372	1466,1470**	1467-1469	1470
St. 4 by Vannøya	70.1127	20.2644	1473,1478**	1474-1476	1477
St. 5 Lyngsfj. outer	69.8836	20.4517	1479,1483**	1480,1481	1482
St. 6 Lyngsfj. inner	69.6339	20.4115	1484,1489**	1485-1487	1488

* LOPC not logging all the way to the bottom

** no water, for calibration of LOPC fluorescence sensor against CTD fluorescence sensor